

intensified and that regional rice improvement programs expand the genetic diversity of their breeding materials. The need for more training of rice scientists and for additional support to national rice research programs was evident to the group.

Below is a list of participants in IRTP monitoring tours during 1977.

1. *Arid regions tour* (Sudan, Egypt, and Pakistan)
 - G. Ghobrial, Sudan
 - M. S. Bald, Egypt

- M. Moafizad, Iran
- A. M. Farkhonde, Iran
- G. McLean, Ford Foundation, Egypt
- M. Rosero, CIAT/IRRI, Colombia
- W. R. Coffman, IRRI
- H. E. Kauffman, IRRI

2. *Nepal and northern India tour*

- A. N. M. R. Karim, Bangladesh
- M. Nasiruddin, Bangladesh
- H. K. Pande, India
- D. N. Borthakur, India
- G. Verma, India
- S. Saran, India

- B. B. Shahi, Nepal
- K. P. Shreshta, Nepal
- D. V. Seshu, IRRI
- J. C. O'Toole, IRRI

3. *Central America and Mexico tour*

- J. I. Murillo, Costa Rica
- W. R. Pazos, Guatemala
- L. H. Aragon, Mexico
- E. Espinosa, Panama
- M. Rosero, CIAT/IRRI, Colombia
- S. K. De Datta, IRRI
- D. V. Seshu, IRRI
- H. E. Kauffman, IRRI

Pest management and control

DISEASES

Potash nutrition and sheath blight disease

S. Kannaiyan and N. N. Prasad, Microbiology Laboratory, Agricultural College, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar, Tamil Nadu, India

The effect of potash application on the development of sheath blight, caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*, was investigated in a pot-culture experiment during the 1976 wet season (June–September) with ADT 31 used as the susceptible rice variety. Muriate of potash as basal

dressing was applied at 0,49,99, 148, 198, and 247 kg K₂O/ha (converted from kg/acre). Nitrogen at 123 kg/ha was applied as urea and phosphorus at 62 kg P₂O₅/ha as superphosphate to all treatments. Disease intensity and yield were recorded.

Potassium application reduced the disease incidence significantly. As the potash levels increased, the disease incidence decreased, with a corresponding increase in yield (see table). Investigation reveals that potash nutrition gives rice resistance to sheath blight.

Sapporo, where natural occurrence of ragged stunt had not been observed.

Of 40 insects that received the supernate injection, 21 survived for 2 weeks afterward. They were used to inoculate seedlings of the rice variety Mihonishiki, at 3 insects/seedling for an inoculation feeding period of 3 days. The same insects were then transferred to inoculate another set of seedlings for 3 days. All 14 inoculated seedlings developed symptoms of the disease.

In addition to supporting the viral nature of ragged stunt, the experiment showed that the injection method can be used in bioassay of the virus.

Effect of potash on the incidence of sheath blight disease. Tamil Nadu, India.

Potash level (kg K ₂ O/ha)	Mean disease index	Decrease in disease over control (%)	Mean grain yield (g/pot)	Increase in yield over control (%)
0	81	–	11	–
49	76	6	11	6
99	65	20	12	15
148	61	24	14	26
198	55	33	15	42
247	49	39	16	50

C.D. (P = 0.01)

Bioassay of rice ragged stunt virus

T. Senboku and E. Shibata, University of Hokkaido, Sapporo, Japan; and E. R. Tiongo and K. C. Ling, International Rice Research Institute

The infectivity of rice ragged stunt virus was determined by the injection method

at the University of Hokkaido, Japan. Fresh leaves of diseased plants of IR3839-1, infected in the Philippines, were macerated in a buffer solution and centrifuged. The supernate was injected by a fine glass capillary into the body of brown planthoppers *Nilaparvata lugens*. The insects had been reared for years in

Ragged stunt disease in Thailand

Praphas Weerapat, rice breeder, and Sompong Pongprasert, rice entomologist, Rice Division, Department of Agriculture, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives, Bangkhen, Bangkok-9, Thailand

Ragged stunt disease, transmitted by *Nilaparvata lugens*, was first noted in Thailand by Dr. E. A. Heinrichs, IRRI entomologist, during an October 1977 visit to the Bangkhen and Rangsit Rice Experiment Stations. It caused serious yield losses in the variety RD7 around Bangkok at the end of the 1977 wet season. About 3,200 ha of RD7 in Chachengsao province, central plains region, were severely infected; in many

fields, 90% of the plants failed to produce normal panicles. Average yields were about 0.4 t/ha; however, the resistant variety RD9 and some traditional tall varieties grown in the area yielded normally. Farmers reported a heavy infestation of brown planthopper at the beginning of the season, but there were

no severe losses from hopperburn.

Much of the affected area was planted by broadcasting pregerminated seed, so plant spacing was close. Surprisingly, transplanted crops of traditional tall, susceptible varieties in adjacent fields were normal.

Symptoms on the diseased plants were

similar to those described in the October 1977 issue of the *IRRI Reporter* except that leaves were not extremely distorted. Stunting was so extensive and severe in some fields that farmers plowed their crops under before flowering so they could plant a dry-season crop. **W**

Pest management and control

INSECTS

A new cage for rearing hopper parasites

*Girish Chandra, Entomology Department,
International Rice Research Institute*

A new cage to rear parasites of rice leafhoppers and planthoppers has been developed. The main disadvantages of the traditional system of rearing hoppers in glass tubes or plastic mylar cages are eliminated in the new cage. Such disadvantages include excessive moisture, difficulty in changing food plants, contamination by soil-inhabiting nematodes, mortality and loss of parasite larvae and pupae (especially those that pupate in the soil), and difficulty in rearing large numbers of hoppers.

The new cage, which is easy to build, is made of a 17 × 12-cm cylindrical transparent plastic container with a removable top (see figure). For aeration, a piece of nylon mesh cloth is fixed to the lid and another to the side window. A vial lid with a plastic screwcap and a large hole in the top is firmly cemented in a hole at the bottom of the container. Thus, the glass vial can be unscrewed and detached while its lid remains attached to the cage. Rice seedling roots are inserted in the water-filled vial and a plastic ring with a small hole, which fits in the vial lid, is fixed around the seedling stems. The space left around the stems is then plugged with cotton. Rice seedlings are easily inserted in the cage through the large hole in the vial lid. A layer of wet cotton spread on the bottom of the cage and covered with filter paper will hold sufficient moisture to maintain the hoppers. Field-collected hoppers are released in the cage through the small holes in the cage walls with an aspirator.

New cage for rearing hopper parasites.

The holes are then plugged with cotton balls. About 100 hoppers can be reared in the cage. Rice seedlings can be changed when necessary and moisture can be maintained by dropping water on the filter paper. The emerged larvae of parasites usually pupate at the bottom of

the cage or on the leaves and can easily be seen through the transparent plastic.

The cage has been very useful for breeding hopper parasites, for observing their behavior and life cycles, and for determining the efficiency of parasites and predators in hopper control. **W**